

EVALUATION OF STRESS HORMONE CORTISOL LEVELS AND BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVELS IN PEDIATRIC ENDOUROLOGICAL SURGERY

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Abstract. *The aim of the study was to evaluate the levels of the stress hormone cortisol and blood glucose levels during endourological surgeries in children. The study is based on an analysis of the results of anesthesia effectiveness in 47 children undergoing endourological surgeries aged 1 to 14 years at Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. The patients were divided into three groups based on the anesthesia technique used. Group 1 (19 children) received General Anesthesia (GA). Group 2 (18 children) received Combined Inhalation Anesthesia (CIA), Group 3 (10 children) received Epidural Anesthesia (EA). The methods of the study included cortisol and blood glucose level analysis. In Group I, an increase in cortisol levels by 55% and 70%, as well as a 31% increase in blood glucose, was likely due to the activation of the nervous and humoral systems in response to surgical aggression. At the same time, the absence of statistically significant changes in cortisol and glucose levels ($p > 0.05$) in Groups II and III indicated adequate anesthesia with endourological methods. A comparative analysis of the results showed that the gradual dynamics of cortisol levels in the blood indicate a moderate activation of adrenal cortex function and the preservation of their functional capacity under combined inhalation anesthesia and combined epidural anesthesia during endourological surgeries in children.*

Keywords: *anesthesia, Stress Hormone, Hemodynamics, Propofol, Sevoflurane.*

Introduction: Among surgical techniques, endoscopy plays a leading role in urological practice. This is largely due to advancements in endoscopic equipment adapted for pediatric use, as well as the minimally invasive nature of these procedures. The significant expansion of endoscopic techniques has increased their diagnostic value while reducing the invasiveness of treatments and interventions.

The introduction of new methods and techniques of endoscopic treatment touches on a wide range of issues in applied medical fields. Primarily, this concerns anesthesiological support, not only as a means of protection from surgical aggression but also for ensuring “surgical comfort” during various endoscopic manipulations.

The solution to modern operative urology tasks is impossible without the creation of highly physiological general anesthesia, and the issue of pain relief during oncological urological surgeries remains highly relevant in the current development of anesthesiology.

From the perspective of assessing surgical stress, endoscopic procedures are considered more organ-preserving and, therefore, less traumatic.

Objective of the Study: To evaluate the levels of the stress hormone cortisol and blood glucose levels during endourological surgeries in children.

Materials and Methods: The study is based on an analysis of anesthesia effectiveness in 47 children undergoing endourological surgeries aged 1 to 14 years at Tashkent Pediatric Medical

Institute. The patients were divided into three groups based on the anesthesia technique. Group 1 (19 children) received General Anesthesia (GA), Group 2 (18 children) received Combined Inhalation Anesthesia (CIA), Group 3 (10 children) received Epidural Anesthesia (EA). The methods included cortisol and blood glucose level studies.

Anesthesia Methodology: Combined general anesthesia with propofol and ketamine. In Group 1, GA was performed. Premedication was administered intramuscularly with Atropine sulfate 0.1% (0.01 mg/kg), Dimedrol 1% (0.1 mg/kg), Sibazon 0.5% (0.3 mg/kg), and Ketamine 5% (3 mg/kg). After 15-20 minutes, a peripheral vein was punctured for intravenous access. Induction was performed with a bolus injection of 1% propofol (2 mg/kg), followed by a 5-minute infusion of 5% Ketamine (3 mg/kg).

Results: The data on the dynamics of cortisol and blood glucose levels are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1 – Dynamics of cortisol levels (* – $p < 0.05$ when compared to Group I)

At the initial stage, cortisol levels were similar, and no statistically significant differences were found between the groups. However, when analyzing cortisol levels at the 2nd and 3rd stages of the study, significantly lower cortisol levels were observed in Groups II and III compared to Group I (Group I – 233 ± 24.2 nmol/L and 255.7 ± 19.7 nmol/L; Group II – 168.8 ± 45.4 nmol/L and 172.7 ± 38.8 nmol/L; Group III – 160.8 ± 9.7 nmol/L and 170 ± 8.2 nmol/L). It is worth noting that the increase in cortisol levels at the 2nd and 3rd stages in Group I patients was 55% and 70%, respectively, compared to baseline values. When analyzing cortisol levels in Groups II and III at the 2nd and 3rd stages, no statistically significant differences were noted ($p > 0.05$).

Baseline glucose levels were similar between the groups ($p > 0.05$). Upon further analysis, blood glucose levels were significantly lower in Groups II and III at the 2nd and 3rd stages compared to Group I (Group I – 5.1 ± 0.9 mmol/L and 5.4 ± 1 mmol/L; Group II – 4.3 ± 0.8 mmol/L and 4.1 ± 0.7 mmol/L; Group III – 4.6 ± 0.7 mmol/L and 4.2 ± 0.9 mmol/L). The increase

in glucose levels at the 2nd and 3rd stages in Group I patients was 31% compared to baseline values.

No statistically significant differences in glucose levels were noted between Groups II and III at the 2nd and 3rd stages ($p > 0.05$).

In Group I patients, the increase in cortisol levels by 55% and 70%, as well as glucose levels by 31%, is most likely related to the activation of the nervous and humoral systems in response to surgical aggression. At the same time, the lack of statistically significant changes in cortisol and glucose levels ($p > 0.05$) in Groups II and III indicates adequate anesthesia with endourological methods. This pattern is associated with a more pronounced blockade of efferent pain impulses in patients from these groups.

Figure 2. Dynamics of glucose levels (– $p < 0.05$ compared with Group I)*

Conclusions. In our study, there was a statistically insignificant increase in the entire spectrum of cortisol indicators during the most traumatic phase of the surgical procedure compared to baseline levels. This indicates that the use of combined inhalation anesthesia and combined epidural anesthesia does not cause functional impairment of the adrenal cortex.

Combined general anesthesia with propofol in combination with ketamine does not have a significant stimulating effect on the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system, and the level of glucocorticoids (GCs) in the plasma usually does not increase. In our study, although a (statistically insignificant) increase in cortisol levels was observed, the indicators did not exceed normal values.

Thus, a comparative analysis of the results of this study showed that the stepwise dynamics of cortisol levels in the blood indicates a very moderate activation of adrenal cortex function and preservation of their functional capacity under combined inhalation anesthesia and combined epidural anesthesia during endourological operations in children. This is achieved through the maximum modulation of stress responses due to adequate sympathetic blockade.

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